

THE IMPACT OF STRESS RESISTANCE ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HEAD OF AN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Abstract. *The article examines stress resistance as a factor in effective management activity. The entire process of the activities of the head of an educational organization depends on its level. The level of adaptability of the head to psychological stress (overload) and the ability to make decisions are indicators of his or her readiness for the position held.*

Keywords: *stress resistance; performance efficiency; head of an educational organization; mental resistance to stress; factors of effectiveness; stress phases; burnout; personal qualities of the head; adaptability; resilience.*

Achieving the goals of an educational organization by increasing the effectiveness of the team's joint activities is a distinctive feature of management activities. The goal of management activities is to ensure the results of the joint work of the educational institution's team. Management activities involve influencing other people to organize their successful interaction. The specificity of management activities is the fact that the object of influence is the subjects who make demands on the subject, such as complete dedication and independence in decision-making, possession of all information and its adequate perception, and forecasting the situation. Each person, being a subject of any type of activity, always sets goals for himself that are specific to the context of the relevant activity.

The manager is a leader in the work collective, where social and psychological relations are formed between employees. It is obvious that the manager should be considered not only within the framework of his administrative role, but also taking into account the whole variety of his socio-political and educational responsibilities. Some studies have shown that in terms of efficiency, the activity in which the manager is not only a superior by position, but is also an informal leader, i.e. one of the team members, dominates. And finally, management activity is specific in terms of internal and external conditions.

Internal conditions include: incorrect definition of performance evaluation criteria; solving and performing multiple tasks simultaneously.

External conditions include: high degree of responsibility for the result obtained; frequent occurrence of stressful situations; uncertainty in terms of information; strict time frames.

The effectiveness of management activities largely depends on the management apparatus and the professionalism of managers. The manager must simultaneously combine both formal and informal leadership qualities, but maintain a distance. Also, the manager must competently build communication, master the techniques of managing it; be able to cope with psychological and physical stress; be resistant to stressful situations, know how to get out of them; have a high level of development of cognitive abilities.

The subject and product of labor in management is information, which after all processing takes the form of a solution, as a result of which it serves as a guide for the implementation of certain actions. The complexity of management is due to the number, scale of problems to be solved, the variety of methods used, and organizational principles. Another difficulty is that new decisions often have to be made under risky conditions, which certainly requires experience and knowledge; moreover, independence and responsibility in making risky decisions play an important role. All responsibility in this case falls on the head of the educational organization, since he is the one who makes decisions on which the well-being of the organization and the material well-being of people depend. The main functions of the management process are: coordination, motivation, control, planning, organization.

The efficiency of management activities is a relative characteristic of the performance of a specific management system, which is reflected in various indicators of the manager as a subject of management, and the actual management activity.

Basic concepts of management efficiency:

- efficiency of the work of managers;
- efficiency of decision-making;
- efficiency of the management and communications system;
- efficiency of the mechanism (method) of management [10].

Efficiency, in turn, depends on many factors: the goal, management styles of managers, relationships in the team, the skills of the manager, the level of work activity. The efficiency of management largely depends on the availability of feedback, that is, the interest of employees in the team. And if we take into account the fact that employees are considered the main source of effective development of the organization, then motivation is necessary and important for them. Highly motivated employees are a close-knit team.

The effectiveness of management activities consists of creative adaptation using the human resources of the organization, where all employees know the motives, tasks and main goal, that is, they support the culture of the organization, which makes it possible to achieve a good result. There are various ways that help us find out how effective the activities of the head of the educational organization are. To obtain effective indicators, it is necessary to have complete and reliable information for making management decisions by the head of the educational organization to promptly identify and eliminate the problem in the process of professional activity, thereby increasing its effectiveness. To identify effectiveness, analytical indicators are used, with the help of which the head of the educational organization can determine how effective his activities are.

It is useful for managers to remember four priority factors of efficiency:

- the current efficiency indicator (the degree of compliance of the activity with the set goal in the current period; this indicator can be determined by comparing data for past periods);
- efficiency dynamics (identifying the reason that caused the problem or decrease in efficiency);
- knowledge of the efficiency dynamics (dynamics is also called a trend, which shows a decrease, increase or no dynamics at all);
- the course of action (measures that need to be applied, used to increase efficiency or, on the contrary, maintain it at the level at which it is (in case of successful efficiency); at the meeting, managers are required to ask questions about the dynamics, indicators and course of action for all parameters).

It should be noted that at present, the level of language training is of great importance for improving managerial competence and expanding the professional capabilities of the head of an educational organization. Everyday reality indicates the increased popularity of foreign languages in Russian society. The public life of the state, its goals, objectives, large-scale transformations could not fail to find a response in the growing need to speak one or more foreign languages. Thus, knowledge of a foreign language has become a professionally necessary tool that shapes personality and opens up prospects for professional self-realization. This competence, without exaggeration, is one of the key ones for a modern manager and is of a communicatively oriented, as well as professionally oriented nature. At the same time, a manager's weak level of proficiency in a foreign language can become a serious obstacle to establishing communicatively oriented connections in professional activities and, as a result, cause a stress reaction in the body. The larger the educational organization, the more responsibilities and tasks are assigned to the manager, and the degree of responsibility also increases. Often, situations occur that require a certain risk, in connection with this, a large number of stressors appear - factors that cause stress.

British psychologist D.Fontana in his classification identified two types of stressors: work-related stressors and off-duty stressors. Work-related stressors include:

- poor organization of work-related activities;
- lack of staff;
- working hours (working overtime and at inconvenient hours);
- solving sudden crisis problems;
- status problems (low status, low salary, insufficient prospects for career advancement);
- overorganization, formalism and meeting fuss (unnecessary rituals and procedures);
- uncertainty and unpredictable developments in the organization [20].

Modern researchers consider the following to be the most significant qualities of a successful leader:

- confidence;
- dominance;
- stress resistance;
- motivation;
- sociability;
- reliability and responsibility.

The manager's self-confidence gives the core to the manager's management activity, since subordinates feel the manager's state. A self-confident manager provides psychological comfort, thereby increasing the team's motivation to work, while a hesitant manager will not be able to inspire confidence in subordinates. Dominance gives the ability to influence subordinates and subordinate them. Subordinates follow the requirements and rules that the manager sets; at the same time, it is necessary to observe not only formal organizational influence, but also take into account informal influence. Stress resistance, emotional stability and personal components of an effective manager of an educational organization are very important, since negative states arise in a manager due to low stress resistance, which affects subordinates and the entire activity of the organization, which in general inevitably entails low work efficiency. It is also necessary to control your emotions for a positive climate in the team. The stress resistance of a manager in management activities can be characterized as "the ability to take a punch." The manager, like all people, is a living person, and therefore can be subject to negative emotional states: despondency, irritation,

anger, but constant suppression of emotions can lead to unfavorable consequences, in particular to the emergence of neuroses and, as a consequence, to psychological burnout, which is the cause of professional deformation of the personality of the head of the educational organization, therefore it is necessary to find timely means for emotional and psychological relief.

The desire for achievements is based on one of the needs - motivation for achievement. The motivation of the manager becomes maximally possible only when he has adequate goals and when he has the necessary resources to achieve them.

Sociability is the basis of organizational and communicative functions, which are the main ones in the structure of management activities. The manager spends most of his working time on communication, from which we can conclude that without sociability it is impossible to have such qualities as the ability to build relationships with people. Developing communication skills is an important part of the self-development of a manager.

Without possessing such qualities as reliability and responsibility, it is impossible to conduct successful management activities, since the relationship between subordinates and managers becomes negative in the event of an inability to "keep their word", that is, in any situation, obligations must be fulfilled.

The managerial activity of the head of an educational organization is often characterized by emotional and neuropsychic stress. Therefore, the problem of maintaining and increasing stress resistance is very relevant and necessary for effective activity, as well as for mental, social and physical well-being. Stress is a companion of conflict, which is present in any team and in the business environment. The main signs of stress are irritability, nervousness, aggression, irascibility, which lead to the devastation of the personality and destructive relationships with people around them, which, in turn, often leads to an imbalance between the individual-personal qualities of a person and the requirements of the professional environment, which negatively affects stress resistance. The effectiveness of performance is largely influenced by the lack of mental resistance to stressful situations, which often leads to the occurrence of stress and leaves a negative imprint on the entire period of professional activity, as well as on the health of the manager. Stress reduces performance, motivation for more active activity, leads to increased anxiety, nervousness, which becomes the cause of conflicts in the team. The main individual characteristic of the content of stress is stress resistance (adaptation). Stress resistance is an adaptation to the impact of unfavorable internal and external factors of the environment and activity. Adaptation is characterized by social, physiological and mental regulation of the functional state. This property manifests itself in a change in a person's behavior and performance. A low level of stress resistance of a manager entails a decrease in the effectiveness of management activities. A high level of stress resistance helps a manager to cope more successfully with stress and its consequences, overcome conflicts, ensuring fruitful work focused on successful professional activity. The formation of stress resistance is an integral condition for social stability.

In summary, it is appropriate to conclude that the concept of stress resistance implies adaptation to the regulation of emerging unfavorable environmental factors and to emerging professional difficulties. The higher the emotional stability, resilience, emotional stability, personal adaptive potential are, the better the head of the educational organization copes with problems. The features of professional activity are characterized by emotional and neuropsychic stress, that is, the head must have a sufficiently high level of locus of control, which generally contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of management activities.

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